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1. Abbreviations

BoP - Balance of Plant

FC - Fuel Cell

FCS - Fuel Cell System

H₂ - Hydrogen

HD – Heavy Duty

N₂ – Nitrogen

O₂ - Oxygen

2. Summary

This document explains in detail the integration process of the chosen FCS into UPV's testbed. The selected FCS is the Nuvera E-60-HD, which was designed to be used mainly for heavy-duty (HD) applications. This system is considered appropriate for the experimental campaign because it can be used both in steady and transient conditions. Additionally, its capability to be sensorized is significantly beneficial for the testing activities.

The integration of the FCS into the testbed is an easy process that has already been done and explained in previous deliverables. However, the present document explains in detail the integration process and the sensorization of the system that will allow an accurate analysis of the obtained results.

3. Fuel cell system integration into the testing facility

The FCS that has been chosen to be tested in the present experimental campaign is the Nuvera E-60-HD, composed of a FC stack and its BoP components, which allow to generate up to 60 kW of electrical power. As explained in previous deliverables, the integration of such a system into the facility required the use of a specific crane able to lift the weight of the FCS. However, the installation process was quite straightforward. Figure 1 shows the final setup of the FCS in the test bench.

Figure 1: Nuvera E-60-HD integrated into the testing facility.

After the integration of the FCS, the final facility is shown in Figure 2. This complex experimental testbed allows to measure the mass flow rate of both air and H₂ going into the FCS. Additionally, the operating conditions (temperature and relative humidity) of the air going into the system can also be measured and controlled, together with the conductivity of the coolant. Regarding the FCS, it is possible to measure the current, voltage and power produced by the stack, as well as the BoP consumed power.

Figure 2: Complete outline of the FCS facility.

Previous deliverables have already explained in detail the commissioning process of this complete facility and its particularities.

4. Sensorization of the testing facility

The previously presented experimental facility provides significant data about the performance of a FCS, considering the existing research context for FCS, as in the present times there exist few available datasets about the performance of an FCS. However, to increase the research value of the testing activities, new sensors are included in the facility.

Figure 3: Schematic of the FCS and the possible measuring points.

Figure 3 shows the FCS and the possible measuring spots. In green, the figure shows the variables that can be measured at the moment. The orange labels stand for the possibility of adding a sensor at that specific spot to record the specified value. The red labels imply that it would be impossible to measure that information with the designed experimental facility. The anode inlet into the system, which is shown in Figure 4, is a closed rigid tube in which it is not possible to place any sensor. The position of a sensor in that tube would compromise its integrity and may produce possible irreversible damage to it.

Figure 4: Anode inlet.

After the start of the validation of the testing facility, the control of the BoP designed by the manufacturer was evaluated. It was determined that, given the advanced stage of the system which is under commercialization and the results obtained, the management of the auxiliary components can be considered optimal for the FCS. The results indicated how the cathode stoichiometry was always enough to avoid reactants starvation and the stack temperature was always kept below 80°C. Avoiding starvation and high temperature implies that the FCS is protected against operating conditions under which a severe loss of performance may appear. Furthermore, the dynamics of the FCS can be adjusted up to the limits imposed by the manufacturer for safety, which gives an additional degree of freedom for the testing activities. In this sense, the already-implemented BoP provides enough performance and flexibility to carry out all the experimental activities planned in the All-In Zero project and this flexibility comes from the fact that the FCS is already in the commercialization stage and has been designed and optimized for heavy-duty vehicle applications.

After a deep analysis into the data that is desired to be recorded during the experimental activities and a large market research, CMT has acquired the required sensors. Depending on their placement or functionality, they can be divided into 5 different groups: cathode circuit, cathode inlet to the stack, cathode outlet, water outlet circuit and cooling circuit.

4.1. Cathode circuit

The conditions going into the cathode system are well known, as they can be established by using the AT1500 from AVL and measured just before the inlet by using the Flowsonix Air. However, inside the circuit, the air goes through different processes that change its conditions.

Firstly, the air goes through a compressor that increases its pressure for a better performance of the FC membrane. It is possible to measure the power used by the compressor, which allows to have a better idea of the efficiency of the system. However, knowing the conditions out of the compressor would allow to understand the process that the air is going through and the heat release that its work produces in the system.

Figure 5: Sensors at the compressor outlet.

The sensor used to measure the temperature is the thermocouple type K Pt100, which will be used to measure this variable in each of the specified measuring spots. Type K thermocouples are the most common type as they provide a cheap solution with a wide range of temperature measurements. The Pt100 is a RTD or Resistive Temperature Devices, which means it has a resistor that changes its value as temperature changes. The reason behind using RTDs instead of common thermocouples is their precision. Thermocouples are cheaper and are capable of being used over 400°C. However, as the expected temperature range will not exceed 80°C, and a precise measurement is required, RTDs represent a better choice.

The pressure sensor used is a relative pressure sensor with a range from 0 to 4 bar (Figure 6). The advantage of choosing these sensors from the testbed manufacturer is that the integration into the FCS facility is much easier.

Figure 6: Connections of the pressure sensors installed.

The humidity sensor used is the EE23 from E+E Elektronik Ges.m.b.H. This sensor has been designed for industrial applications and has a temperature range from -40 to 180°C. This sensor is shown in Figure 7 and has a range from 0 to 100% of relative humidity with a precision of $\pm 1.3\%$.

Figure 7: Humidity sensor EE23.

4.2. Cathode inlet

The conditions of the air in the stack are of high importance to ensure an efficient and safe operation. These data will be measured after the cathode circuit heat exchanger, just before the air flows into the stack.

The temperature, humidity and pressure sensors will be placed as shown in Figure 8Figure 9. The sensors used in the facility are the same model as the ones that have already been explained.

Figure 8: Cathode inlet sensorization.

4.3. Cathode outlet

The cathode outlet contains the gases that remain after the electrochemical reaction. Knowing the conditions of these gases will help understand the processes that take place in the membrane. Thus, a thermocouple and pressure sensor will be added in that spot as shown in Figure 9. The selected pressure sensor has a relative pressure range from -1 to 2.5 bar.

Figure 9: Sensors at the cathode outlet.

The presented figure also shows the probe that has been added to measure the gas species in the cathode outlet. The percentage of each gas in the cathode can provide valuable information about the safety of the process (H_2), the degradation taking place in the membrane (CO_2), the crossover species (H_2 , N_2 and O_2) or other aspects of the electrochemical reaction in the membrane.

In addition, a mass flowmeter will be added in the cathode outlet to measure the amount of gas flowing out of the system. Together with the gas analyzer, which allows to measure the percentage in volume of each gas, this will provide valuable information about the species remaining after the electrochemical reaction.

The mass flow meters that will be placed in the cathode outlet are the Yokogawa Vortex Flowmeter of 40mm and 100mm. This device is shown in Figure 10. It has a temperature operating range from $-40^{\circ}C$ to $250^{\circ}C$ and a gas accuracy of $\pm 1\%$.

Figure 10: Mass flowmeter at the cathode outlet.

4.4. Water outlet circuit

Finally, an important amount of water is generated in the energy generation process of a FCS. As shown in Figure 2, this water is conducted to the water network to be reused. Additionally, the generated water vapor is condensed in an aftercooler to be used again as part of the network. To quantify the amount of liquid water and condensed water, two different mass flow meters are added to the system (Figure 11).

Figure 11: Mass flow meter to measure the water output.

These devices would allow the quantification of this water, which may be used to get a better understanding of the system, but also to design possible auto-humidification strategies in the FCS.

The installed mass flow meters from RS PRO have an operating range from 0.25 to 6.5 l/min and have a measuring range of 500 Hz (up to 20 bar).

4.5. Cooling circuit

In order to identify the thermal characteristics of the FCS, the FCS provides a value of FC stack temperature. Nevertheless, the cooling circuit performance also depends on other parameters such as the coolant mass flow rate. Therefore, apart from the already-available thermocouples located at the inlet and at the outlet of the external heat exchanger, a mass flow rate measuring device was installed along the cooling circuit (Figure 12).

Figure 12: Mass flowmeter at the cooling circuit.

Additionally, the compressed air at the cathode circuit goes through a heat exchanger located after the compressor in which the cooling system decreases the temperature of the air so that it is appropriate for the stack and safe for the operation of the membrane. To understand the heat exchanged in this process, some temperature sensors are placed in the inlet and outlet of heat exchanger as shown in Figure 13.

Figure 13: Heat exchanger temperature sensors in the cathode circuit.

5. Verification of the testing facility

Finally, after the sensorization of the system was finished, the testing activities were ready to be performed. However, before starting the experimental campaign, some verification tests will be carried out.

For this purpose, both a steady and a transient example test in standard conditions were performed to ensure that the sensor are functioning in the correct way and its installation did not damage or disturb the performance of the testbed in any way.

As an example of the results obtained in these tests, Figure 14 shows the temperature measured in the stack and in the new cathode outlet sensor. This last test dynamic test shows no abnormal performance, and it allows to confirm the appropriate functioning of the experimental facility after the installation of the new sensors.

Figure 14: Temperature measurements in a dynamic test.

As explained in detail in previous deliverables, the capability of testing both steady and dynamic conditions is a key factor in the current experimental campaign, and it makes the study suitable to be used for the characterization of FCS for HD applications.